

Supplementary Materials for

An Inverse Design Framework based on Finite Element Method for 4D Printed Structures: Theory, Implementation, and Applications

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S1 Experimental results of soft gripper design

Supplementary Fig. 1 | Maximum displacement measurements of six fingers , tested over three independent experimental trials. Displacements were analyzed using ImageJ. The desired max displacement is 16 mm. The actual max displacement is 14.592 mm, 15.104 mm, 14.180 mm, 15.184 mm, 15.738 mm, 14.414 mm.

Supplementary Videos S1-S5

Supplementary Video S1

Deformation process for numerical simulation case 1.

Supplementary Video S2

Deformation process for numerical simulation case 2.

Supplementary Video S3

First experimental demonstration of the gripper design.

Supplementary Video S4

Second experimental demonstration of the gripper design.

Supplementary Video S5

Third experimental demonstration of the gripper design.